

Proposed New CO2 Emissions Mitigation Mechanism

Joseph Nowarski, M.Sc., ME – Energy Conservation Expert

Version 1.1.1, 1 November 2022

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7270802

all versions DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7270801

Abstract

MM, the new CO2 Emissions Mitigation Mechanism (Mitigation Mechanism) proposed in this work, is the CO2 mitigation program assisting the countries to reach the 1.5°C-2.0°C global warming limit in the year 2100.

Considering climate justice, the countries which will not reduce their CO2 emissions to the limit in a specific year will buy carbon credits. The new CO2 Emissions Mitigation Mechanism introduces an efficient way to buy carbon credits and an efficient way to use carbon credits.

This work proposes a procedure to guarantee constant carbon credit price, known in advance. This procedure does not require the involvement of carbon traders, reducing the time between the creation of emissions reduction and the actual money transfer to the project participants.

The carbon credits issued by the operating organization will be sold to the countries which did not reduce their CO2 emissions to the required limit in the specific year. These carbon credits will have a constant price without a time limit, known in advance publicly.

The money received from the buying country will be used as an incentive for CO2 mitigation projects and will be transferred directly to the project participant instead of carbon credits. Considering the 50\$ carbon credit cost the maximum cumulative cost of the carbon credits proposed in this work will be 0.61% of the

world cumulative GDP in the period 2025-2100. The maximum yearly cost of the carbon credits will be in the year 2037, 0.70% of the world's GDP.

Keywords: climate change, global warming, climate justice, CO2 emissions, Clean Development Mechanism, CDM, Certified Emissions Reduction, CER, CERs

Glossary

Ave	average
BAU	Business-as-Usual scenario
BL	baseline
CO2	emissions of Carbon Dioxide, CO2
Cp\$	CO2 emissions per GDP, tCO2/\$GDP
CpC	CO2 emissions per capita, tCO2/y,cap (ton CO2 per year, per population of the country)
Global Warming	global surface temperature change over land+ocean above 1850-1900 baseline (°C)
GtCO2	Giga-ton of CO2, 10 ⁹ ton, 10 ⁹ ton, 1,000,000,000 ton of CO2
IO	International Organization running the New CO2 Emissions Mitigation Mechanism Program (International Organization)
MM	Proposed New CO2 Emissions Mitigation Mechanism (Mitigation Mechanism)
MMC	CO2 emissions reductions certified by the New CO2 Emissions Mitigation Mechanism (Mitigation Mechanism Certificate), 1 metric ton of CO2
MtCO2	Mega-ton CO2 = 10 ⁶ ton, 10 ⁶ ton, 1,000,000 ton CO2
tCO2	metric ton CO2 = 10 ⁶ gram CO2

Necessary Change in CO2 Emissions to Reach 1.5°C-2.0°C Global Warming Limit in 2100

The publications "*Necessary Change in CO2 Emissions per Capita to Reach 1.5°C-2.0°C Climate Change Limit in 2100*" [1] and "*Necessary Change in CO2 Emissions per GDP to Reach 1.5°C-2.0°C Climate Change Limit in 2100*" [2] analyze required CO2 emissions reduction to reach the 1.5°C-2.0°C Global Warming limit in 2100. Not all countries will be able to reach this target, like countries whose main source of CO2 emissions is oil refineries or countries that did not develop efficient public transport. Considering climate justice, the countries which will not reduce their CO2 emissions according to the above limits in the specific year will buy carbon credits. The new CO2 Emissions Mitigation Mechanism (MM) described in this work introduces an efficient way to buy carbon credits and an efficient way to use the carbon credits.

New CO2 Emissions Mitigation Mechanism - MM

In most carbon credits programs, the price of the carbon credits is unknown before the planning and construction of the emissions reduction projects.

The uncertain price of carbon credits is a major barrier to GHG mitigation.

After the mitigation project is completed the project participant receives certificates, which can be sold to the carbon credits trader at a lower price than the trader will finally receive. The market prices of carbon credits vary with time and may be much lower than originally expected. This procedure causes serious risk to the project participant regarding the planned income from carbon credits and loss of income related to carbon credits trader's fees.

This work proposes a different procedure to guarantee constant carbon credit price, known in advance. This procedure does not require the involvement of carbon traders, reducing the time between the creation of emissions reduction and the actual money transfer to the project participants.

MM, the new CO₂ Emissions Mitigation Mechanism (Mitigation Mechanism) proposed in this work, is the CO₂ mitigation program assisting the countries to reach the 1.5°C-2.0°C global warming limit in the year 2100.

The MM may be run by International Organization (IO), like UN-FCCC-CDM or World Bank.

Countries that did not reduce their CO₂ emissions according to the required limit in the specific year, should buy carbon credits from IO, even if the IO has not yet any CO₂ mitigation project.

The carbon credits sold by the IO are MMCs - CO₂ emissions reductions certified by the new CO₂ Emissions Mitigation Mechanism (Mitigation Mechanism Certificate), 1 metric ton of CO₂ each.

The MMC has constant value known in advance publicly, equal for all countries. IO will issue CO₂ mitigation certificates (MMCs) to the buying country.

IO will use the money received from the buying country as an incentive for CO₂ mitigation projects according to the criteria. Once the CO₂ mitigation project is registered by the IO, the project participant may submit a verified monitoring report to the IO. After the verified monitoring report is approved, the IO will transfer the money equivalent to the CO₂ emissions approved, directly to the project participant's bank account. The amount of money the IO will pay to the project participants for each ton of CO₂ equals the price of MMC sold to the buying countries less some small fees to run the MM.

IO operation procedure

- buying country transfers to IO amount of money relevant to the missing CO₂ mitigation to the annual target, based on the constant MMC price
- IO sends MMCs to the buying country
- Project participant submits the project to IO for registration
- IO approves the project registration
- Project participant submits verified monitoring report to IO
- IO approves the verified monitoring report

- IO transfers to the project participant amount of money according to the approved CO2 emissions reduction and constant MMC price
- There will be some MMC price difference between the price for the buying country and the price paid to the CO2 mitigation project participants, to cover the IO operation cost

Advantages of the MM - new CO2 Emissions Mitigation Mechanism

- The MMC price is constant and guaranteed without time limits and without any conditions, which dramatically decreases the financial risk of the CO2 mitigation project
- The guaranteed MMC price is known to the project participants before the decision and planning of the project, allowing exact financial analysis
- The project participants will receive the full amount of the MMCs price without paying fees to carbon credit traders
- There is no need for contracts between the project participants and carbon credits traders
- Project participants will get the money much faster than in other carbon credit programs

Carbon Market Prices

Publication [3] contains CERs (UN FCCC CDM) and EUAs (EU ETS) prices. The publication includes the following information regarding the CERs prices in the period 2008-2012: *"From a peak near Euro 30/t CO₂, carbon traded roughly in the Euro 10 – 15 range before falling steadily toward Euro 5 at the beginning of 2012"*. The publication includes also an estimation of "carbon social cost" which is 15.7-65.0 \$/tCO₂.

Internet site "*Trading Economic - EU Carbon Permits*" [4] includes a chart of "*EU Carbon Permits (EUR)*" from April 2005 to current (October 2022).

Table 1 - EU Carbon Permits prices 2005-2022 [4] [EUR]

EUR	
Apr-05	16
May-06	27
Jul-07	0.5
Jun-08	29
Apr-13	3
Jul-19	28
Mar-20	17
Jun-22	90
Oct-22	81
Min	0.5
Max	90
Ave this table	32
Ave(Min-Max)	45

Publication [5] contains a dataset of EU ETS prices.

Table 2 - EU ETS prices 2021-2022 [5]

	EUR/tCO2	\$/tCO2	Date
From			04/01/21
to			15/09/22
Min	31.62	38.18	18/01/21
Ave	65.86	74.95	
Max	98.01	114.65	19/08/22
Latest	71.85	71.71	15/09/22

Considering the above, this work applies the MMC price of 50 \$/tCO₂, constant for the period 2022-2100 and beyond.

The MMC price for the buying country is slightly higher considering the IO operation cost, estimated as 1%, 50.50 \$/tCO₂ cost for the buying country.

Maximum Volume of MM Program

Publications [1] [2] analyze the CO₂ emissions per capita (CpC) and per GDP (Cp\$) determining the necessary annual change in CpC and Cp\$ to reach the 1.5°C – 2.0°C Global Warming limit in 2100.

Table 3 - Maximum volume of the MM program [1] [2]

Cumulative CO2 emissions in 2100 without international transport		BAU 4.1°C	2.0°C	1.7°C	1.5°C
annual change in CpC	%/y	0.078%	-4.46%	-7.85%	-17.00%
according to CpC [1]	MtCO2(BL1875)	5,672,105	2,678,071	2,275,981	2,002,048
Δ to BAU	MtCO2(BL1875)		-2,994,034	-3,396,124	-3,670,057
annual change in Cp\$	%/y	-1.315%	-5.91%	-9.34%	-18.00%
according to Cp\$ [2]	MtCO2(BL1875)	5,672,105	2,677,536	2,275,412	2,007,987
Δ to BAU	MtCO2(BL1875)		-2,994,569	-3,396,692	-3,664,117
Max	MtCO2(BL1875)		-2,994,569	-3,396,692	-3,670,057
MMC price to buying countries	\$/MMC		50.50	50.50	50.50
MMCs cost (2025-2100)	M\$MMC/75y		151,225,733	171,532,955	185,337,874
Cumulative world GDP [6]	M\$GDP/75y	30,410,471,114			
MMC cost per GDP	\$MMC/\$GDP		0.50%	0.56%	0.61%

The maximum MM Program cost is 0.50%-0.61% of the world's expected cumulative GDP in the period 2025-2100.

The CO2 emissions mitigation projects probably will increase the world GDP by more than 0.6% of the GDP, however, for the conservativeness of the estimation, this is not considered in this work.

Annual Cost of MMC per GDP

Chart 1 - Annual Cost of MMCs per GDP (50.50\$ per MMC) [6] [\$/MMC/\$GDP]

The maximum yearly cost of MMCs to GDP is 0.695% (\$MMC/\$GDP) in 2037 [6].

Contribution of Mitigation Projects to GDP - Example of Solar Water Heaters in Israel

Table 4 - Contribution of mitigation projects to GDP - example of solar water heaters in Israel

GDP 2020 [2]	359,908,802,382	\$GDP/y
SWH	2,000,000	units
Electricity saving [7]	1,200	kWh/y per unit
National saving	2,400,000,000	kWh/y
EF [8]	0.570	tCO2/MWh
Emissions Reduction	1,368,000	tCO2/y
MMCs cost	69,084,000	\$/y
MMCs to GDP	0.019%	
SWH unit cost	1,000	\$
lifetime	10	y
national SWH product	200,000,000	\$/y
SWH to GDP	0.056%	
SWH/MMC	2.9	\$/y

EF – Emission Factor of the last CDM project in Israel (7777) = 0.570 tCO2/MWh [8]

In the above example, the contribution of the mitigation project to the GDP is much higher than the cost of carbon credits. As mentioned before, the contribution of the CO2 emissions mitigation projects to GDP is not considered in this work for the conservativeness of the estimations.

References

1. Necessary Change in CO2 Emissions per Capita to Reach 1.5°C-2.0°C Climate Change Limit in 2100 – Joseph Nowarski, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7264419
2. Necessary Change in CO2 Emissions per GDP to Reach 1.5°C-2.0°C Climate Change Limit in 2100 – Joseph Nowarski, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7264421
3. INFORMING THE CARBON MARKET POLICY DIALOGUE: THE EMISSIONS TRADING SYSTEMS AT A GLANCE, World Bank, DOI: 10.2870/323576 <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340455667>
4. Trading Economic - EU Carbon Permits <https://tradingeconomics.com/commodity/carbon>
5. EU Carbon Price Tracker, The latest data on EU ETS carbon prices <https://ember-climate.org/data/data-tools/carbon-price-viewer/>
6. Dataset CO2 Emissions per GDP Forecast 2020-2100 - Joseph Nowarski, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7264415
7. Solar Israel: A practical and legislative model – Joseph Nowarski, Renewable Energy World - March-April 2000 p.92-99, DOI:10.6084/m9.figshare.21443073
8. UN-FCCC CDM project 7777

* * *